

Appendix

The Survey

Section	Item	Formulation	Answer type
Introduction	IN01	Have you ever heard about GenAI before this survey?	Single choice (Yes, No)
	IN02	Have you used GenAI before this survey?	Single choice (Yes, No)
	IN03	For what purposes have you used GenAI?	Single choice (Work only, Leisure only, Both work and leisure, I have never used GenAI)
	IN05	Have you used GenAI in the past two weeks?	Single choice (Yes/No)
	IN06	What are the rules of using GenAI in your workplace? It is...	Single choice (Mandated, Voluntary, Forbidden, I don't know)
	IN07	Does your employer/organization provide access to GenAI tools?	Single choice (Yes, No, I don't know)
	IN08	Does your employer/organization have its own GenAI tools?	Single choice (Yes, No, I don't know)
	Performance Expectancy (PE)	PE_1	GenAI is useful in my job/for my job.
PE_2		Using GenAI increases my productivity.	Likert Scale (1-7)
PE_3		Using GenAI increases my job performance.	Likert Scale (1-7)
PE_4		Using GenAI enhances my effectiveness on the job.	Likert Scale (1-7)
Effort Expectancy (EE)	EE_1	My interaction with GenAI is clear and understandable.	Likert Scale (1-7)
	EE_2	I find GenAI easy to use.	Likert Scale (1-7)
	EE_3	Learning to use GenAI is easy for me.	Likert Scale (1-7)
	EE_4	It is easy for me to become skillful at using GenAI.	Likert Scale (1-7)

Social Influence (SI)	SI_1	People who influence my behavior think that I should use GenAI.	Likert Scale (1-7)
	SI_2	People who are important to me think that I should use GenAI.	Likert Scale (1-7)
	SI_3	My supervisor is very supportive of the use of GenAI.	Likert Scale (1-7)
	SI_4	In general, the organization has supported the use of GenAI	Likert Scale (1-7)
Facilitating Conditions (FC)	FC_1	I have the resources necessary to use GenAI.	Likert Scale (1-7)
	FC_2	I have the knowledge necessary to use GenAI.	Likert Scale (1-7)
	FC_3	GenAI is compatible with other systems I use.	Likert Scale (1-7)
	FC_4	A specific person (or group) is available for assistance with GenAI difficulties.	Likert Scale (1-7)
Behavioral Intention (BI)	BI_1	I intend to use GenAI in the future.	Likert Scale (1-7)
	BI_2	I will always attempt to use GenAI in my daily life.	Likert Scale (1-7)
	BI_3	I plan to continue using GenAI frequently.	Likert Scale (1-7)
Experience: Organization	OR_Amount	In how many organizations have you worked?	Text Entry
	OR_Total_Time	How long did you work in each organization?	Text Entry
	OR_Time	How long have you been with your current organization?	Dropdown selection (1-20+ years)
	OR_Type_1	The number of employees in the organizations.	Multiple choice (Small: 1-50 employees, Medium: 51-250 employees, Large: 250+ employees)
	OR_Type_2	The nature of the organizations.	Multiple choice (Public, Private, NGO, Other)
	OR_Type_3	The sector or field of the organizations.	Dropdown selection (1-10+)
	OR_Type_4	The location of the organizations.	Dropdown selection (1-20+)

	OR_Type_5	The primary language used within the organizations.	Dropdown selection (1-10+)	
Experience: Job Role	JO_Amount	How many different job roles have you held?	Text Entry	
	JO_Total_Time	What was the tenure time in each role?	Text Entry	
	JO_Time	How many years have you been working in your current job role?	Dropdown selection (1-20+ years)	
	JO_Type_1	How many different areas or departments have you worked in?	Dropdown selection (1-20+)	
	JO_Type_2	How different were your job roles you have had?		
		In terms of working in various areas or departments.		Likert Scale (1-5)
		In terms of having roles in different areas in the organization (horizontally).		Likert Scale (1-5)
	JO_Type_2	In terms of having roles at different levels in the organization (vertically).		Likert Scale (1-5)
		JO_Type_4	What is the average number of people you were responsible for leading in your job roles?	Dropdown selection (1-20+)
	JO_Type_5	How complex were your job roles you have had?		
		In terms of coordinating with many teams or stakeholders and having decision-making authority and management duties.		Likert Scale (1-5)
		In terms of having specific needs, such as interacting with different types of people or stakeholders		Likert Scale (1-5)
		In terms of working in different locations.		Likert Scale (1-5)
In terms of challenging conditions, like tight deadlines.		Likert Scale (1-5)		
Experience: Task	Task Choice	What is your main task in your current job role?	Single choice (Acquisition, Analyze, Authoring, Co-authoring, Dissemination, Expert Search, Feedback, Information organization, Information search, Learning, Monitoring, Networking, Service search, Other)	
	Task Amount	On average, how many times do you complete the specific task you selected in the previous question each week?	Dropdown selection (1-20+)	
	Task Time	On average, how much time do you spend completing the task?	Dropdown selection (1-20+ hours)	
	Task_Type_1	How different are your tasks?		
		My tasks are repetitive.		Likert Scale (1-5)
		My tasks vary.		Likert Scale (1-5)
		My tasks always take the same amount of time.	Likert Scale (1-5)	

		My tasks always have the same workload.	Likert Scale (1-5)
		My tasks have different workload.	Likert Scale (1-5)
		My tasks require the same skills.	Likert Scale (1-5)
		My tasks require different set of skills.	Likert Scale (1-5)
		I interact with the same stakeholder for my tasks.	Likert Scale (1-5)
		I interact with different stakeholders for my tasks.	Likert Scale (1-5)
	Task_Type_2	How complex are your tasks?	
		My tasks require significant decision-making efforts and judgment calls.	Likert Scale (1-5)
		My tasks require specialized knowledge or technical skills.	Likert Scale (1-5)
		My tasks are heavily dependent on the completion of other tasks or external factors.	Likert Scale (1-5)
		My task requirements are frequently changing.	Likert Scale (1-5)
		My tasks require processing of information and problem-solving.	Likert Scale (1-5)
Gender	DE01	Please specify your gender.	Single choice (male, female, other)
Age	DE02	Please enter your age (in years).	Text Entry
Education	DE03	What is your highest level of education?	Single choice (No education qualification, Secondary school leaving certificate, University entrance qualification, completed vocational training, Bachelor's degree, Master's degree, Doctorate, Other)
Note: Likert scale (1-7) 1= strongly disagree; 4 = neutral; 7 = strongly agree			